

THE INCREASING IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION SECURITY

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Abstract

The shortest definition of information security should be built on the fact that the concept of 'information' is important and increasing rapidly, and the definition of information should be given in a clear and understandable way. Recording information on paper or other media is important as it is a collection of data that can be understood and transmitted. At the same time, ideas that are transmitted, recorded, and published in the human brain in any way, formally or informally, form the basis of "knowledge", whether they are real and imaginary products. This is where the concept of security, "security of information" appears.¹ It would be correct to say that knowledge is the upper level of information or data. It is no coincidence that knowledge has been defined by many theorists as "information with meaning". If we transform information into a usable or useful activity, it becomes knowledge which creates a necessity for the stages we have mentioned.² If phone numbers are data, a meaningful phone book is information. By recognizing a number in the directory, we can understand who this number belongs to.³ Identifying information provides access to real information by going through the stages of examination, evaluation, synthesis and decision.^{4,5}

Keywords: *Information, Information Security, Cyber Security, Confidentiality of Information*

1. Several Approaches to the Concept of Security with Theories

Despite many fundamental concepts, information security is possible to affect the concept of relational security positively or negatively. It also includes mechanisms of positive protection, facilitation and sometimes provision.⁶ Thus, security policy can embody an important concept of freedom and seek to improve positions. By arguing that the contextual factor should be defined, information security also describes the freedom limits of perpetrator (preventive condition). In other words, what the owner of the information and the party who wants to access the information are free to do, be or not, will change depending on the need for the security of the information. In other words, meaningful discussions of freedom need to be placed in context and should be based on proper information.

Whether the same can be said for security is a matter of discussion here. Meaningful discussions about security are based on proper contextual information about whose security is at stake, what value or interest is to be secured, what risk or threat is posed, and who is in the best position to protect and provide it. The concept of security itself does not include this information.⁷

2. Online Information Security Especially for the Internet World

There are some specific steps that can be taken to protect your online information, identity and privacy. For example, using a unique password for each site is considered the first step. That way, if one of your passwords is compromised, the others can still be safe. Using complex passwords is just as important as never sharing them. If it is possible, using multi-factor authentication (MFA) helps protect even more. Using a password manager is one of the recommendations made in terms of information security. Using an encrypted password manager to store passwords makes it easy to access and use a complex, unique password for each site. (“Data Privacy Day 2020 | Information Security Office”)

Recognizing what is shared is fundamental to information security. Controlling privacy settings in all apps and social media accounts relies on making sure they are set to share with the intended person, not just what is asked. It is a clear recommendation that it would not be correct to rely on the default settings.

The requirement to protect the date of birth and phone number is another critical issue among the principles of information security. These are valuable information

used for verification, and not sharing them publicly is one of the truths that should be prioritized for the above rankings. An online service or site may want to share critical information and assessing whether it is important enough to call for it will be an important pre-processing step. There are no real secrets online. Using the postcard or billboard test was again decided as a correct recommendation by expert authorities: If the answer to the question "Do you mind if everyone reads a message or post?" is negative, it would be the right decision not to share it.

The increasing interest in the concept of security and especially its relation to human rights in the last decade has led to the adoption of a number of new security laws at the international level in response to a series of terrorist attacks around the world.⁸ There seem to be some suggestions in these discussions:

- We must give up some of our freedoms in the name of security. (Michael Ignatieff)

This sentence is questioning whether the 'era of human rights has arrived' and the limitation of rights means accepting 'less bad'. Although security and human rights protecting our freedoms express a compromise, the idea of 'balancing' security and freedom together is open to criticism. These discussions are largely based on the concept of security, unable to define exactly

what it is. Conceptually, it is assumed that the meaning of "security" is clearly understood and can be accepted as it is. There is an important academic literature in the disciplines of criminology and international relations that tries to define the concept of security. Because security consists of the relationship between democracy, crime control and the "security industry".⁹

3. Conceptual Structure of Security

Surprisingly, a few attempts have been made to define the conceptual structure of security and they are political. But they are not conceptual discussions. Most studies also presuppose an international relations context, and it is not clear how the definitions can be applied to other contexts such as human rights or the environment. In summary, there is no acceptable, universally valid definition of the concept of security. It is necessary to present a context-free analysis of the concept of security. This conceptual discussion is not limited to any area where security issues arise like human security, international security, national security or personal security.¹⁰

Analyzing security in a single context will be unsystematic and run the risk of being partial or one-dimensional. It will also do

not address how different contexts affect each other. "Conceptual analysis of security should apply equally well to all applications of the concept." ("2.pdf - See discussions stats and author profiles for this ...") The actual application of the analysis is beyond the scope of this article. The existing literature on security brings to light several aspects of security that can be used when developing a conceptual definition.^{11 12}

Security can be both negative and positive, and there is the idea that security is based on a 'security policy' that decides how instrumental or conservative security is in any given context. The discussion also includes the importance of the concept of 'threat' and the scope of (military and non-military) threats we may face, the importance of the concepts of interests and values, and the range of interests and values that may arise. At the same time, there are various levels (international, national and individual) to which security may be relevant. "My primary argument is that security is a relational concept." ("2.pdf - See discussions stats and author profiles for this ...")

4. Relational Security Concept

The concept of relational security is like Peter Digeser's formal concept of security in that it is not substantive. ("2.pdf - See discussions stats and author profiles for this ...")

...”) To understand any security discussion, it is necessary to find the following:

- a. Security for whom,
- b. security of what (a value or interest),
- c. security against what (a threat or risk) and
- d. Security by whom (provider of protection).

The concept of security is also mentioned at the level where the concept of security is applied (international, national, group, individual) and about the interest or value of these to be secured. Following concepts will require further consideration; whether the security is silent about the threats and risks involved and who should supply the protection and how. Therefore, these concepts are also context sensitive in themselves. Contextual security debates rely on a combination of political theory and policy decisions or a "security policy" to decide which interests or values should be protected or promoted against what risks and threats, how and by whom. This makes security an adaptive concept and helps explain why it has come to be used in so many ways in so many different fields.¹³

5. Regarding the Mainstream

Approach

The meaning of the concept will be decided when we reach a proper understanding of persons, states, systems or institutions. An alternative possibility is to understand security as a purely formal concept. (“2.pdf - See discussions stats and author profiles for this ...”) The problem with the mainstream approach is that it tries to transfer a fixed content to a term that necessarily allows for variability. The concept of formal security refers to a reasonable expectation that ‘value of what one has’ will persist in the future.

Digester has found a major problem with the most tried security definitions. Although, relational is a more proper label than formal. A relational concept describes relationships between other things. In a sense, it is helpful or supportive. Defining security as a relational concept rather than a formal one has two advantages. First, this terminology highlights the need for more input – information about the proper agent, interest, threat, and provider – more effectively than the formal concept.

6. Goals of Information Security

Information security basically targets the following three elements:

- i. Confidentiality¹
- ii. Integrity
- iii. Availability

In these concepts; confidentiality can be explained as the fact that the information is not available for access by unauthorized persons. It is possible to explain the concept of integrity with the accuracy and completeness of the information. Usability means that information is available when needed. Along with responsibility, access control and security elements appear as supporting factors in terms of information security. The concept of reliability arises when access control is perceived as the whole of the permissions to access the relevant resource. This is, an example, the stimuli for a computer's design in addition to its terms and conditions and communication system. Because the sustainability of an institution or organization to gain added value and to realize the conditions of competition to make a profit will require the product, market, technology and organization. This kind of information also reminds us that how important is the necessity of the security.

7. Precautions to be Taken for Security

In addition to personal information, requested identity-related elements are within the scope of personal data: name, surname, date of birth and place of birth accordingly are identity-related information, including phone number, motor vehicle license plate, social security number, passport number, curriculum vitae and picture. All data that makes the person identifiable directly or indirectly, such as image and sound recordings, fingerprints, genetic information, IP address, e-mail address, device IDs, hobbies, preferences, interacted persons, group memberships and family information are within the scope of personal data.¹⁴

Taking necessary precautions to prevent information and technology fields from becoming more vulnerable requires especially important steps in terms of security and especially information security. Some concepts and results expected because of these studies are possible:

- (a) Collecting information and data,
- (b) Centralized collection of unrelated data,
- (c) Analysis of information, including data mining, with advanced

- technology and data matching method, and an increase in the ability to produce new data,
- (d) Access, sharing and transfer of information;
 - (e) Categorizing the quality and quantity of personal data according to risks,
 - (f) Especially for world intelligence agencies, usage of information and data on terrorist and criminal organizations to take measures against their activities and attacks,
 - (g) To preserve individual information and data in matters such as bank and credit card frauds at the highest-level about protection needs.

8. Personal Information Security

Measures

- a. Manipulations related programs,
- b. Fraud and imitation studies,
- c. Obtainment of access tools by unauthorized persons,
- d. identity theft,
- e. Obtainment of commercial information by malicious persons,
- f. activities serving intelligence activities,
- g. Illegal activities such as stalking and surveillance,
- h. hacking,

- i. Harmful software such as viruses, worms, trojan horses (Slammer, MsBlaster, Sobig etc.)¹⁵,
- j. Activities that need details about spyware (spyware),
- k. Sending spam e-mails,
- l. Malicious attacks that stop or suspend the service

9. Conclusion

While a more general scrutiny is always needed, there is a need for originality in claims about security enhancement measures from the point of view of conceptual analysis. Due to the nature of security, the feeling of such measures as a threat or risk should not only inform that they exist, but also include which values or interests will be secured. The issues related to the person or institution's safety that is in danger and choosing protector should be decided after the definition of security concept. Although security issues require detailed research, foresight and separate topics that include possibilities, it is also important that they can support the measures and policies to be taken by the states. ¹⁶ Regarding the fact that giving importance to safety has become a priority over the past decade, it's important to know that now is the best time. Security itself should not be the focus of policy discussion,

as the claim that security is a relational rather than essential concept would cast doubt on the meaning of 'security' in its nominal form. It is more important to ask questions on how values and interests can be preserved and enhanced in the future. The security concepts, details, especially personal and corporate security issues related to information along with the digital world development and evaluation of possible risks require many new studies and also reveal the necessity of updating old studies.

10. References

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11. Footnotes

1. Information security, on the other hand, is all the efforts to create a secure information processing platform to protect the information from unauthorized access while keeping and transporting data or information in electronic media.
2. Information security, on the other hand, is all the efforts to create a secure information processing platform to protect the information from unauthorized access while keeping and transporting data or information in electronic media without destroying its integrity.
3. According to another definition, information security is the protection of data, programs and all kinds of information kept on disk, communication network, backup units or elsewhere.
4. Although it is possible to reproduce the definitions related to information security, we can list a few of these definitions as follows.
5. It aims at information security, business continuity, minimizing loss in inevitable disaster situations, and protecting the confidentiality, accessibility and integrity of resources considered as the building blocks of companies under all circumstances.
6. Depending on the underlying political theory, the concept of relational security may also be instrumental – it means not just protecting what we already have.
7. Security is a relational concept because it defines the relationship between these four factors and derives its meaning from them in any context. A parallel point has been made by Digeser, who introduced what he calls an official notion of security. A fundamental concept of security (which is the mainstream approach) sees this knowledge as part of the concept of security itself: McCallum Jr 'Negative and Positive Freedom' (1967) *Philosophical Rev* 312-334 319; Digeser 'The Concept of Security' (presented at the American Political Science Association Annual Meeting September 14, 1994).
8. These measures have been criticized for their impact on human rights and have sparked debate about the appropriate 'balance' to be struck between human rights and security concepts in the media, government, academia and courts.
9. Its reflection on the internal security of the society and the reactions to internal security threats is the first issue. The second covers national security and armed conflicts and studies, and within this framework includes the idea of 'human security' promoted by the United Nations. A limited discussion of security can also be found in the moral philosophy literature on social justice and welfare, and this is important about property rights. In fact, there has been a long and lively academic debate about the importance and role of 'security', dating back to political theorists such as Adam Smith, Thomas Hobbes, Jeremy Bentham and John Locke.
10. Rather, it is consistent with a variety of ideological positions and contexts: 'The definition may advance the status of such a theory, but only succeed if it explains and illuminates them all.'
11. These features include: the idea that security is not a 'material' concept, the flexibility inherent in security, J Raz *The Morality of Freedom* (Clarendon Oxford 1986) (discussing the

nature of rights). Halpin describes such definitions as 'virtuous': A Halpin 'Concepts, Terms, and Fields of Inquiry' (1998) *Legal Theory* 187-205 195-198. The implementation of the right to personal security and its implications for other fields are discussed in chapter six and at the conclusion of my doctoral thesis.

12. For example, P Digeser 'The Concept of Security' (presented at the American Political Science Association's Annual Meeting September 14, 1994); L Freedman 'The Concept of Security', ME Hawksworth and M Kogan (eds) *Encyclopedia of Government and Politics* (2nd ed Routledge London 2003) 30-41; DA Baldwin 'The Concept of Security' (1997) 23 *Rev of Intl Studies* 5-26. For example, P Digeser 'The Concept of Security' (presented at the American Political Science Association Annual Meeting September 14, 1994); B Buzan *People, States, and Fear: An Agenda for International Security Studies in the Post-Cold War Era* (2nd ed Harvester Wheatsheaf New York 1991).

13. For example, 'The Good of Security' (CUP Cambridge 2007) and K Booth *Theory of World Security* (CUP Cambridge 2007) 27P Digeser 'The Concept of Security' (Presented at the Annual Meeting) in I Loader and N Walker *Civilizing Security American* 14

September 1994 from the Political Science Association).

14. The right to the protection of personal data is among the basic human rights and freedoms, and it is of vital importance in terms of protecting the personality of the person, the principle of the rule of law and deepening democracy. The main purpose of protecting private life, including personal data, with constitutional guarantees is to allow the free development of human personality, to provide an autonomous space where the individual can be alone with himself and his relatives, and where he cannot be disturbed by the state or others. (Establishment of information security management system and information security risk analysis within the scope of TS ISO/IEC 27001 information security management standard - Hasan YILMAZ, Internal Auditor, Istanbul University)

15. 10 T.C. Presidency, State Supervisory Board, 27/11/2013, Audit Report No. 2013/3, p.778,779

16. Security discourse also limits the willingness of courts to review some government actions, a clearer conceptual framework would increase transparency and discourage hiding behind vague concepts such as 'security' to increase government power and curtail civil liberties.